

ANALISIS KEMAMPUAN REPRESENTASI MATEMATIS MAHASISWA

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Submitted
2021-01-03

Accepted
2021-04-26

Published
2021-04-30

Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk mengetahui bagaimana kemampuan representasi matematis mahasiswa STKIP Melawi. Metode penelitian yaitu kualitatif deskriptif dengan bentuk penelitian survei. Subjek penelitian berjumlah 25 orang dari populasi mahasiswa Pendidikan Matematika yaitu 51 orang. Subjek dipilih secara *simple random sampling* tanpa mengetahui kemampuan awal matematika setiap mahasiswa. Teknik pengumpulan data menggunakan teknik tes dan wawancara. Instrumen penelitian yang digunakan yaitu lembar soal tes kemampuan representasi dan pedoman wawancara. Analisis data yang digunakan yaitu reduksi data, penyajian data, dan penarikan kesimpulan. Mahasiswa diwawancarai setelah selesai menjawab soal-soal yang diberikan. Penyajian hasil olah data dalam bentuk deskripsi yang kemudian ditarik kesimpulan. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa mahasiswa yang menjawab soal sesuai indikator menggunakan representasi visual (gambar) untuk menyelesaikan masalah matematika dikategorikan tinggi dan mahasiswa yang menjawab soal sesuai dengan indikator melakukan translasi dari representasi verbal (tulisan) ke dalam representasi visual (gambar) matematika dengan tulisan dikategorikan rendah.

Kata Kunci: kemampuan; representasi matematis; bangun datar.

Abstract

The research objective was to determine how the mathematical representation abilities of STKIP Melawi students. The research method was descriptive qualitative with a survey research form. The research subjects were 25 people from the Mathematics Education student population, namely 51 people. Subjects were selected by simple random sampling without knowing the initial mathematical ability of each student. Data collection techniques using test and interview techniques. The research instrument used was a representation ability test question sheet and interview guidelines. The data analysis used was data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion. Students are interviewed after answering the questions given. Presentation of the results of data processing in the form of descriptions which then draw conclusions. The results showed that students who answered questions according to the indicators using visual representations (pictures) to solve math problems were categorized as high and students who answered questions according to the indicators translated from verbal representations (written) into visual representations (pictures) of mathematics with writing categorized as low.

Keywords: ability; mathematical representation; plane figure.